

Some special cases of Convexity

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Abstract. We study a special case of a convex operator

Introduction

Let A denote the class of all analytic functions $f(z)$ in the unit disk

$$U = \{z \in \mathbb{C}, |z| < 1\}$$

And $S = \{f \in A: f, \text{univalent in } U\}$

We denote by S^* the class of starlike functions in A normalized by $f(0) = f'(0) - 1 = 0$, and

$$\Re \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} > 0, (z \in U)$$

A function $f \in U$ is called β -spirallike if

$$\Re \left(e^{i\beta} \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \right) > 0, (z \in U)$$

for a real number $\beta (-\frac{\pi}{2} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2})$.

Also we denote by K the class of convex functions in A normalized by $f(0) = f'(0) - 1 = 0$, and

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} + 1 \right\} > 0, (z \in U)$$

In this paper we will consider the following integral operators and study their convexity.

$$F_n(z) = \int_0^z t^{\frac{(\Re\alpha_1)^2 + \Re\alpha_1 - 1}{\Re\alpha_1}} \left(\frac{f_1(t)}{t}\right)^{\alpha_1} \dots t^{\frac{(\Re\alpha_n)^2 + \Re\alpha_n - 1}{\Re\alpha_n}} \left(\frac{f_n(t)}{t}\right)^{\alpha_n} dt$$

And

$$G_n(z) = \int_0^z \left(\frac{f_1(t)}{t}\right)^{\alpha_1} \dots \left(\frac{f_n(t)}{t}\right)^{\alpha_n} dt$$

To prove our results, we need the following lemma

Lemma 1.1. (see[1]). $f(z)$ is β -spirallike if and only if there is a starlike function $s(z)$, such that

$$\frac{f(z)}{z} = \left(\frac{s(z)}{z}\right)^\alpha \quad (z \in U),$$

Where $\alpha = e^{-i\beta} \cos\beta$.

Convexity of $F_n(z)$ and $G_n(z)$

Theorem 2.1. Let $F_n(z)$ be the integral operator given by (1.1), for $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, if

(i) f_j is β -spirallike for every $j, (-\frac{\pi}{2} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2})$.

(ii) $\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{\cos\beta_j} < n + 1$.

(iii) $\alpha_j = e^{i\beta_j}$.

Then $F_n(z)$ is convex.

Proof. By Lemma 1.1 for every $f_j(z)$ there exists a starlike function $s_j(z)$ such that

$$\frac{f_j(z)}{z} = \left(\frac{s_j(z)}{z} \right)^{\gamma_j}, \text{ where } \gamma_j = e^{-i\beta_j} \cos\beta_j$$

Now, using (2.1) and (1.1) with simple calculations we find:

$$F_n(z) = \int_0^z \left(t^{1-\frac{1}{\cos\beta_1}} (s_1(t))^{\cos\beta_1} \right) \dots \left(t^{1-\frac{1}{\cos\beta_n}} (s_n(t))^{\cos\beta_n} \right) dt$$

We calculate the first and second derivatives of F_n

$$F_n'(z) = \left(z^{1-\frac{1}{\cos\beta_1}} (s_1(z))^{\cos\beta_1} \right) \dots \left(z^{1-\frac{1}{\cos\beta_n}} (s_n(z))^{\cos\beta_n} \right)$$

and

$$F_n''(z) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_j} \right) z^{-\frac{1}{\cos\beta_j}} (s_j(z))^{\cos\beta_j} + z^{1-\frac{1}{\cos\beta_j}} \cos\beta_j (s_j(z))^{\cos\beta_j-1} s_j'(z) \right] \\ \times \prod_{k=1, k \neq j}^n \left(z^{1-\frac{1}{\cos\beta_k}} (s_k(z))^{\cos\beta_k} \right)$$

From (2.3) and (2.4) we get

$$\frac{F_n''}{F_n'} = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_j} \right) \frac{1}{z} + \frac{\cos\beta_j s_j'(z)}{s_j(z)}$$

this implies

$$\frac{zF_n''(z)}{F_n'(z)} + 1 = \cos\beta_1 \left(\frac{zs_1'(z)}{s_1(z)} + \frac{1}{\cos\beta_1} \right) + \dots + \cos\beta_n \left(\frac{zs_n'(z)}{s_n(z)} + \frac{1}{\cos\beta_n} \right) + 1 - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_1} - \dots - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_n}$$

from (2.6) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \Re \left(\frac{zF_n''(z)}{F_n'(z)} + 1 \right) \\ &= \cos\beta_1 \Re \left(\frac{zs_1'(z)}{s_1(z)} + \frac{1}{\cos\beta_1} \right) + \dots + \cos\beta_n \Re \left(\frac{zs_n'(z)}{s_n(z)} + \frac{1}{\cos\beta_n} \right) + 1 - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_1} - \dots - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_n} \end{aligned}$$

But $s_j(z) \in S^*$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, so $\Re \left(\frac{zs_j'(z)}{s_j(z)} \right) > 0$. We apply this affirmation in (2.7) and we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \Re \left(\frac{zF_n''(z)}{F_n'(z)} + 1 \right) &> \cos\beta_1 \frac{1}{\cos\beta_1} + \dots + \cos\beta_n \frac{1}{\cos\beta_n} - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_1} - \dots - \frac{1}{\cos\beta_n} + 1 \\ &= n + 1 - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{\cos\beta_j} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by the hypothesis (ii) of Theorem 2.1, we obtain that $F_n(z)$ is convex which completes the proof \square

Now by choosing a fixed β -spirallike function in Theorem 2.1 we get:

Corollary 2.1 Let $f(z)$ be β -spirallike, $(-\frac{\pi}{2} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2})$, if

(i) $\alpha = e^{i\beta}$.

(ii) $\cos\beta > \frac{n}{n+1}$, (n is a positive integer).

Then:

$$\int_0^z t^{n \left(\frac{(\Re\alpha)^2 + \Re\alpha - 1}{\Re\alpha} \right)} \left(\frac{f(t)}{t} \right)^{an} dt$$

is a convex function

If we put $n = 1$ in Theorem 2.1 we get:

Corollary 2.2 Let $f(z)$ be β -spirallike, $(-\frac{\pi}{6} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{6})$, if $\alpha = e^{i\beta}$

Then:

$$\int_0^z t^{\frac{(\Re\alpha)^2 + \Re\alpha - 1}{\Re\alpha}} \left(\frac{f(t)}{t} \right)^\alpha dt$$

is a convex function.

Theorem 2.2 Let $G_n(z)$ be the integral operator given by (1.2), for $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, if

(i) f_j is β -spirallike for every j , $(-\frac{\pi}{2} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2})$.

(ii) $\sum_{j=1}^n \cos\beta_j < 1$.

(iii) $\alpha_j = e^{i\beta_j}$.

Then $G_n(z)$ is convex.

Proof. From (2.1) and (1.2) we can find that

$$G_n(z) = \int_0^z \left(\frac{s_1(t)}{t}\right)^{\cos\beta_1} \cdots \left(\frac{s_n(t)}{t}\right)^{\cos\beta_n} dt$$

Now, we evaluate $G'_n(z)$ and $G''_n(z)$, we obtain:

$$G'_n(z) = \left(\frac{s_1(z)}{z}\right)^{\cos\beta_1} \cdots \left(\frac{s_n(z)}{z}\right)^{\cos\beta_n}$$

And

$$G''_n(z) = \sum_{j=1}^n \cos\beta_j \left(\frac{s_j(z)}{z}\right)^{\cos\beta_j-1} \left(\frac{zs'_j(z) - s_j(z)}{z^2}\right) \prod_{k=1, k \neq j}^n \left(\frac{s_k(z)}{z}\right)^{\cos\beta_k}$$

Which implies

$$\frac{G''_n(z)}{G'_n(z)} = \cos\beta_1 \left(\frac{s'_1(z)}{s_1(z)} - \frac{1}{z}\right) + \cdots + \cos\beta_n \left(\frac{s'_n(z)}{s_n(z)} - \frac{1}{z}\right)$$

So,

$$\frac{zG''_n(z)}{G'_n(z)} + 1 = \cos\beta_1 \frac{zs'_1(z)}{s_1(z)} + \cdots + \cos\beta_n \frac{s'_n(z)}{s_n(z)} - \cos\beta_1 - \cdots - \cos\beta_n + 1$$

And

$$\Re\left(\frac{zG''_n(z)}{G'_n(z)} + 1\right) = \cos\beta_1 \Re\frac{zs'_1(z)}{s_1(z)} + \cdots + \cos\beta_n \Re\frac{s'_n(z)}{s_n(z)} - \cos\beta_1 - \cdots - \cos\beta_n + 1$$

But $s_j(z) \in S^*$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, so $\Re\left(\frac{zs'_j(z)}{s_j(z)}\right) > 0$. We apply this affirmation in (2.16) and we obtain:

$$\Re\left(\frac{zG''_n(z)}{G'_n(z)} + 1\right) > \cos\beta_1 \cdot 0 + \cdots + \cos\beta_n \cdot 0 - \cos\beta_1 - \cdots - \cos\beta_n + 1 = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^n \cos\beta_j$$

Hence, by the hypothesis (ii) of Theorem 2.2, we obtain that $G_n(z)$ is convex which completes the proof \square

Now by choosing a fixed β -spirallike function in Theorem 2.2 we get:

Corollary 2.3 Let $f(z)$ be β -spirallike, $(-\frac{\pi}{2} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2})$, if

(i) $\alpha = e^{i\beta}$.

(ii) $\cos\beta < \frac{1}{n}$, (n is a positive integer).

Then:

$$\int_0^z \left(\frac{f(t)}{t}\right)^{n\alpha} dt$$

is a convex function.

If we put $n = 1$ in Theorem 2.2 we get:

Corollary 2.4 Let $f(z)$ be β -spirallike, $(-\frac{\pi}{2} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2})$, if $\alpha = e^{i\beta}$

Then:

$$\int_0^z \left(\frac{f(t)}{t}\right)^\alpha dt$$

is a convex function.

References

1. M. Abramowitz and I. A. Stegun (Eds.), Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables, Dover Publications Inc., New York, 1965.
2. A. A. Attiya, Some applications of Mittag-Leffler function in the unit disk, Filomat 30(7) (2016), 2075-2081. <https://doi.org/10.2298/FIL1607075A>
3. D. Bansal and J. K. Prajapat, Certain geometric properties of the Mittag-Leffler functions, Complex Var. Elliptic Equ. 61(3) (2016), 338-350. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17476933.2015.1079628>
4. T. Bulboacă and G. Murugusundaramoorthy, Univalent functions with positive coefficients involving Pascal distribution series, Commun. Korean Math. Soc. 35(3) (2020), 867 – 877. <https://doi.org/10.4134/CKMS.c190413>
5. N. E. Cho, S. Y. Woo and S. Owa, Uniform convexity properties for hypergeometric functions, Fract. Calc. Appl. Anal. 5(3) (2002), 303-313.
6. P. L. Duren, Univalent Functions, Grundlehren der Mathematischen Wissenschaften Series 259, Springer Verlag, New York, 1983. [7] M. El-Deeb, T. Bulboacă and J. Dziok, Pascal distribution series connected with certain subclasses of univalent functions, Kyungpook Math. J. 59 (2019), 301-314. <https://doi.org/10.5666/KMJ.2019.59.2.301>
7. B. A. Frasin, An application of an operator associated with generalized Mittag-Leffler function, Konuralp J. Math. 7(1) (2019), 199-202.
8. B. A. Frasin, T. Al-Hawary and F. Yousef, Some properties of a linear operator involving generalized Mittag-Leffler function, Stud. Univ. Babeş-Bolyai Math. 65(1) (2020), 67 – 75. <https://doi.org/10.24193/subbmath.2020.1.06>
9. B. A. Frasin, T. Al-Hawary and F. Yousef, Necessary and sufficient conditions for hypergeometric functions to be in a subclass of analytic functions, Afr. Mat. 30(1-2) (2019), 223-230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13370-018-0638-5>
10. H. J. Haubold, A. M. Mathai and R. K. Saxena, Mittag-Leffler functions and their applications, J. Appl. Math. 2011(2011), Article ID 298628. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/298628>
11. V. Kiryakova, Generalized Fractional Calculus and Applications, Pitman Research Notes in Mathematics Series 301, Longman Scientific & Technical, Harlow, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1994.
12. E. Merkes and B. T. Scott, Starlike hypergeometric functions, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. 12 (1961), 885-888.

13. G. M. Mittag-Leffler, Sur la nouvelle fonction $E(x)$, C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris 137(1903), 554 – 558.
14. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, Subordination results for spiral-like functions associated with the Srivastava-Attiya operator, Integral Transforms Spec. Funct. 23(2) (2012), 97-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10652469.2011.562501>
15. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, D. Răducanu and K. Vijaya, A class of spirallike functions defined by Ruscheweyh-type q -difference operator, Novi Sad J. Math. **49**(2)(2019),59 – 71. <https://doi.org/10.30755/NSJOM.08284>
16. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, K. Vijaya and S. Porwal, Some inclusion results of certain subclass of analytic functions associated with Poisson distribution series, Hacet. J. Math. Stat. 45(4) (2016), 1101-1107. <https://doi.org/10.15672/HJMS> . 20164513110
17. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, Subclasses of starlike and convex functions involving Poisson distribution series, Afr. Mat. 28(2017), 1357-1366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13370-017-0520-x>
18. S. Porwal and M. Kumar, A unified study on starlike and convex functions associated with Poisson distribution series, Afr. Mat. 27(5) (2016), 1021-1027. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13370-016-0398-z>
19. M. S. Robertson, On the theory of univalent functions, Ann. of Math. (2) 37(2) (1936), 374-408.
20. Salah, Jamal, Hameed Ur Rehman, and Iman Al-Buwaiqi. "The Non-Trivial Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function through Taylor Series Expansion and Incomplete Gamma Function." *Mathematics and Statistics* 10.2 (2022): 410-418.
21. Rehman, Hameed Ur, Maslina Darus, and Jamal Salah. "Graphing Examples of Starlike and Convex Functions of order β ." *Appl. Math. Inf. Sci* 12.3 (2018): 509-515.
22. Salah, Jamal Y., and O. M. A. N. Ibra. "Properties of the Modified Caputo's Derivative Operator for certain analytic functions." *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 109.3 (2014): 665-671.
23. Jamal Salah and Maslina Darus, On convexity of the general integral operators, An. Univ. Vest Timis. Ser. Mat. -Inform. 49(1) (2011), 117-124.
24. Salah, Jamal. "TWO NEW EQUIVALENT STATEMENTS TO RIEMANN HYPOTHESIS." (2019).
25. H. Silverman, Starlike and convexity properties for hypergeometric functions, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 172 (1993), 574-581. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmaa.1993.1044>
26. H. M. Srivastava, G. Murugusundaramoorthy and S. Sivasubramanian, Hypergeometric functions in the parabolic starlike and uniformly convex domains, Integral Transforms Spec. Funct. 18 (2007),511 – 520. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10652460701391324>
27. L. Spaček, Contribution à la théorie des fonctions univalentes, Časopis Pro Pěstování Matematiky **62**(1932), 12 – 19.
28. Salah, Jamal Y. "A new subclass of univalent functions defined by the means of Jamal operator." *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS) Vol* 108 (2018): 389-399.
29. Jamal Y. Salah On Riemann Hypothesis and Robin's Inequality. International Journal of Scientific and Innovative Mathematical Research (IJSIMR). Volume (3) 4 (2015) 9-14.
30. Salah, Jamal. "Neighborhood of a certain family of multivalent functions with negative coefficients." *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math* 92.4 (2014): 591-597.
31. Salah, Jamal, and Maslina Darus. "A note on Starlike functions of order α associated with a fractional calculus operator involving Caputo's fractional." *J. Appl. comp Sc. Math* 5.1 (2011): 97-101.
32. J. Salah, Certain subclass of analytic functions associated with fractional calculus operator, Trans. J. Math. Mech., 3 (2011), 35–42. Available from: <http://tjmm.edyopress.ro/journal/11030106.pdf>.

33. Salah, Jamal. "Some Remarks and Propositions on Riemann Hypothesis." *Mathematics and Statistics* 9.2 (2021): 159-165.
34. Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "The consequence of the analytic continuity of Zeta function subject to an additional term and a justification of the location of the non-trivial zeros." *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* 9.3 (2020): 1566-1569.
35. A. Swaminathan, Certain sufficient conditions on Gaussian hypergeometric functions, *Journal of Inequalities in Pure and Applied Mathematics* 5(4) (2004), Article ID 83, 10 pages.
36. A. Wiman, Über die nullstellen der funktionen $E_{\alpha}(x)$, *Acta Math.* 29 (1905), 217-134.
37. Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "An Alternative perspective to Riemann Hypothesis." *PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION* 57.9 (2020): 1278-1281.
38. Salah, Jamal Y. "A note on the Hurwitz zeta function." *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)* 101.12 (2017): 2677-2683.
39. Jamal Y. Salah. Closed-to-Convex Criterion Associated to the Modified Caputo's fractional Calculus Derivative Operator. *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)*. Vol. 101, No. 1, pp. 55-59, 2017, DOI: 10.17654/MS101010055.
40. Jamal Y. Salah, A Note on Riemann Zeta Function, *IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, vol. 06, no. 02, pp. 07-16, February 2016, URL: [http://iosrjen.org/Papers/vol6_issue2%20\(part-3\)/B06230716.pdf](http://iosrjen.org/Papers/vol6_issue2%20(part-3)/B06230716.pdf)
41. Jamal Y. Salah, A Note on Gamma Function, *International Journal of Modern Sciences and Engineering Technology (IJMSET)*, vol. 2, no. 8, pp. 58-64, 2015.
42. Salah, Jamal, and S. Venkatesh. "Inequalities on the Theory of Univalent Functions." *Journal of Mathematics and System Science* 4.7 (2014).
43. T. R. Prabhakar, A single integral equation with a generalized Mittag – Leffler function in the kernel, *Yokohama Math. J.* 19 (1971), 7 – 15.
44. Jamal Salah. Subordination and superordination involving certain fractional operator. *Asian Journal of Fuzzy and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 1, pp. 98-107, 2013. URL: <https://www.ajouronline.com/index.php/AJFAM/article/view/724>
45. Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "Two Conditional proofs of Riemann Hypothesis." *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)* 49.1 (2020): 74-83.
46. Salah, Jamal. "Fekete-Szego problems involving certain integral operator." *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology-IJMTT* 7 (2014).